

THE MAIN ISSUES OF IMPROVING MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF CAPITAL MARKET DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation. In this article, the main issues of improving management in the context of capital market development, as well as the implementation of a number of practically important works on improving the mechanisms of capital market operations in our republic in recent years, are considered.

Key words. Capital market, economic entities, privatization of state property, overnight operations, currency trading.

Today and in the near future, success depends on the development of the capital market and the privatization of state property, reducing the influence of the state on the activities of economic entities, and improving management in the activities of privatized economic entities, and the development of large business structures and prospects for the development of entrepreneurial activities.

In this regard, in the Decree No. PF-60 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022, in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the development of the capital market was recognized as one of the necessary conditions for ensuring the stability of macroeconomic growth rates, in particular, in the next 5 years, the turnover of the stock market should be 200 million US dollars to 7 billion US dollars, gradual liberalization of capital movement in our country and privatization of large enterprises and their shares (shares), including through the stock exchange, completion of transformation processes in commercial banks with state shares, private sector in bank assets by the end of 2026 In order to increase its share to 60%, to attract

foreign investment funds to the capital market, the tasks of placing state or corporate Sukuk bonds in the stock markets in accordance with international legislation and standards have been set. This creates the need to identify current problems in all segments of the capital market and develop scientifically based ways to solve them.

It should be recognized that in recent years in our republic, a number of works of practical importance have been carried out on the improvement of mechanisms for the implementation of operations in the capital market. Including:

- From the beginning of 2022, the practice of pre-announcing the quarterly schedule of bonds issued by the Central Bank and the Ministry of Finance was launched;
- the practice of calculating interest rates for overnight transactions based on a calendar day rather than a working day was introduced;
- a continuous auction using the existing fixing ("fixing") method for determining the exchange rate
 - switched to the "matching" method;
- calculations on currency trading were brought into line with international standards, and as a result, T+1 (next working day) and T+2 (next second working day) forms were introduced for calculations, etc.

In addition, according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-101 dated April 8, 2022:

transition to automation of production and management processes (ERP) systems in order to optimize corporate management, increase liquidity in the corporate securities market;

wide introduction of modern methods of corporate management, including the "compliance" control system, in state-owned enterprises and commercial banks;

prevention of corruption by ensuring the transparency of the procurement

system, training and improving the qualifications of State management and corporate management personnel, wide introduction of modern methods of corporate management in state-owned enterprises;

Adopting advanced foreign experience in introducing social and corporate governance (ESG) accountability systems as the main areas of activity of supervisory boards of enterprises with state participation;

Attracting independent members, including foreign experts, to the supervisory board of enterprises with state participation to be transformed;

In order to train independent members of the Supervisory Board, develop a Code of Professional Conduct for them and improve the system of maintaining a national register of independent members, organize an association of independent members of the Supervisory Board based on their experience and support from advanced top managers, experts, international financial organizations;

In order to ensure the effectiveness of the supervisory board's work, introducing incentives depending on the level of using modern standards and methods of corporate management and increasing the quality indicators of corporate management; It will be necessary to develop a system of performance indicators (KPIs) for monitoring board activity.

The above-mentioned tasks lay the groundwork for the further development of the capital market in our country, the creation of a national methodology necessary for raising the level of privatization and evaluating the effectiveness of the corporate management system, and the formation of a systematic approach to the corporate management system in joint-stock companies. Therefore, training of high-level management personnel in the field of capital market, privatization and management, formation of a system of regular improvement of their qualifications remains a priority direction in the development of this field.

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